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CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND PURCHASE INTENSION TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD

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ABSTRACT

The development of Organic food is still infant stage in India. It is necessary to know about the consumer attitude towards Organic food, based on consumer attitude model factors such as Consumer knowledge, Environmental concern, personal norms, subjective norm and consumer purchase intension are measured which allow us to find the consumer attitude and purchase intension on Organic food. Consumers differ from one another; they will have different ideas, taste, perception, likes and dislikes, attitude in simple term it is thought oriented, if consumer has positive thought on organic food it will create the purchase intension.

Keywords: Infant, Consumer attitude, Environmental concern, Personal norms, subjective norms, thought oriented.

Introduction:

The development in organically produced products is significantly growing in throughout the world; it absorbs the consumer's attention through its benefiting factors such as food safety, environmental friendly, healthier, does not contain chemical pesticide, additives and artificial flavoring. Organic products demand rose up due to the concerns on conventional agricultural method, food safety, chemical pesticide, additives, health issues and artificial flavoring.

Lifetime of Organic Product depends on the consumers, they have to understand the importance of the organic products, should start purchasing the organic products regularly, it increase the demand. Lyon et al 2001¹ said consumers should show their positive response to organic products to sustain its growth otherwise it will be future less.

Based on Consumer Attitude Model:

Consumer concerns on environment is increasing, consumers seeking for the green products to safe guard from chemical added foods, on other aspects, issue on health is a major concerns for consumers, especially in food habits. Health consciousness plays a vital role in consumer mind when they purchase any food products – Yin et al., 2010². Attitude of consumer also relies on Knowledge or information, based on their past knowledge or others knowledge consumers react –Yin et al., 2010.

Thogersen and Zhou’s study 2012³, Consumer attitude can be determined based on demographic variable such as age, gender and income. To add more Magnusson et al., 2001⁴ said young people giving priority to organic food to overcome health and environment factor, female respondents has more health concerns than male to purchase organic food.

Consumers Uncertainty feels and lacks of information significantly disturb their attitude - Thogersen 2007⁵, when a consumer has a feel of uncertainty on the consequences of organic food, they look for social aspects or subjective norms – Jager, 2000⁶. When a individual evaluate their decision on his /her own way is known as personal norms – Aertsens et al., 2009⁷.

Purpose of the Study:

Irin Sutha & Solomon T/ Consumer Attitude and Purchase intension towards Organic Food

This study is to investigate the influential factors on consumer attitude towards organic food and how the attitude influences consumer purchase intention.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To know the Consumer Attitude towards organic food
2. To Find the Influential factors on consumer attitude towards organic food
3. To know how attitude influences consumer purchase intention

Research Methodology

The research work is empirical in nature. A survey questionnaire designed and distributed under Random sampling method. 100 valid samples are considered for the study. Books and websites constitute the secondary data. Model and Factors are developed on the basis of Review of Literature.

Review of Literature:

Attitude is created on the base of experiences it can be changed when a fresh experience arise Ajzen, 2001; Chen, 2007; Armstrong, 2009⁸. When a person hearing a loud noise continuously it creates a negative attitude on sound Solomon et al., 2010⁹

Gracia and de Magistris 2007¹⁰ Positive attitude towards organic food in health issues and environmental benefits, high level of income and level of education on organic food purchase intension Tarkiainen and Sundqvist 2005¹¹ concluded that there is a significant relation between the attitude of purchasing organic food and the intention to buy.

Analysis and Discussions:

Indicating Cronbach's Alpha as reliability tool to validate the data:

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.937	28

Inference:

The reliability for 28 items is 0.937. Even if one of the 28 items is deleted the Cronbach's Alpha value will be reduced. This indicates that the reliability for all items is higher.

Indicating ANOVA between Gender and Attitude towards Organic food:

Attitude towards organic Food		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F Value	Sig
I feel it is good buy organic food	Male	49	3.84	.773	5.735	0.19.
	Female	51	4.22	.808		
	Total	100	4.03	.810		
I think it is wise to buy organic food	Male	49	3.96	.735	2.371	.127
	Female	51	4.20	.800		
	Total	100	4.08	.774		
I think it is important to buy organic food	Male	49	3.92	.759	4.043	.047
	Female	51	4.24	.815		
	Total	100	4.08	.800		

Inference:

H1- There is a significant difference between groups based on gender and Attitude towards organic food

It is inferred from the above table that the p-value of the variables, I feel it is good buy organic food and I think it is important to buy organic food are less than the table value at 95 % level of significance. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference between gender and Attitude towards organic food.

Indicating Mean and Standard deviation for respondent's on Consumer Attitudes towards Organic food:

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	I pay a lot of attention to my health	The health aspect is very important in my food choice	I believe that organic food contains more natural ingredients than conventional food	I believe that organic food is good for my health than conventional food
Mean	4.09	4.00	4.05	4.04
N	100	100	100	100
Std. Deviation	.793	.816	.783	.764

Inference:

Above table shows there is a difference in level of agreement among respondents hence using the rate scale (1) Strongly disagree (2), Disagree (3), Neutral, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree. Below 1 to less than 1.5 considered to be - Strongly disagree, more than 1.5 to less than 2.5 - Disagree, more than 2.5 to less than 3.5 - Neural, more than 3.5 to less than 4.5 - Agree, more than 4.5 – Strongly agree. I pay a lot of attention to my health, The health aspect is very important in my food choice, I believe that organic food contains more natural ingredients than conventional food, I believe that organic food is good for my health than conventional food are agreed therefore dominantly proved on consumer attitude favor on organic food.

Indicating Independent T-test between Gender and Consumer knowledge:

Consumer knowledge	Gender	N	Mean	Sig
My knowledge about organic food is sufficient	Male	49	4.10	.026
	Female	51	4.24	
knowledge about organic food is based on previous experience	Male	49	3.98	.545
	Female	51	4.12	
overall, I have a positive experience/impression about organic food	Male	49	4.02	.927
	Female	51	4.14	

Inference:

H0- There is no significant difference between groups based on Gender and Consumer knowledge on organic food

It is inferred from the above table that the p-value of the variables knowledge about organic food is based on previous experience, overall, I have a positive experience/impression about organic food are greater than the table value at 95 % level of significance. Hence Null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between gender and consumer knowledge on organic food, the mean value of my knowledge about organic food is sufficient, overall, I have a positive experience/impression about organic food, knowledge about organic food is based on previous experience are dominantly agreed between Gender and Consumer knowledge.

Table indicating Factor analysis on Environmental concern, Personal Norms and Subjective Norms:

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
I pay a lot of intention to the environment	1.000	.759
The environmental aspect is very important in my food choice	1.000	.915
I believe that organic food is more environmental friendly than conventional food	1.000	.896
I feel I should choose organic food instead of conventional food	1.000	.841
I get a good conscience about myself if I choose organic food	1.000	.777
I believe that choosing organic food is a right decision	1.000	.828
When it comes to choosing organic food, I behave as others do	1.000	.896
Due to the impact of social pressure	1.000	.857
People likes me influence to choose Organic food	1.000	.778
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Inference:

From table it is found that the 9 variables exhibit the variance limitation from 0.759 to 0.915 which is 76% to 91.5%. Thus these variables can be reduced to predominant factors.

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Indicating Mean and Standard deviation for respondent's on Monthly income and Consumer purchase intension:

Monthly Income		I would buy organic food products in the near future	I plan to buy organic food products in regular basics	I intend to buy organic food products for my long term health benefits	I intend to buy organic food products because they are more concern about food safety	I intend to buy organic food products because they are more environmentally friendly	I intend to buy organic food products because I am concerned about animal welfare
5,000 - 10,000	Mean	3.13	3.00	3.25	3.25	2.87	3.00
	N	8	8	8	8	8	8
	Std. Deviation	1.356	1.309	1.389	1.389	1.246	1.414
10,001 - 20,000	Mean	3.58	3.67	3.58	3.75	3.75	3.83
	N	12	12	12	12	12	12
	Std. Deviation	.515	.778	.793	.754	.754	.835
20,001 - 30,000	Mean	4.00	3.91	3.91	4.09	4.21	4.15
	N	33	33	33	33	33	33
	Std. Deviation	.866	.879	.879	.723	.650	.619
30,001 - 40,000	Mean	3.85	3.85	4.00	3.92	4.04	3.96
	N	26	26	26	26	26	26
	Std. Deviation	.675	.675	.748	.744	.720	.662
40,001 & Above	Mean	4.48	4.43	4.43	4.29	4.43	4.43
	N	21	21	21	21	21	21
	Std. Deviation	.602	.598	.598	.561	.507	.507
Total	Mean	3.94	3.90	3.95	3.98	4.05	4.03
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Std. Deviation	.851	.870	.880	.804	.809	.797

Inference:

Above table shows there is a difference in level of agreement among respondents hence using the rate scale (1) Strongly disagree (2), Disagree (3), Neutral, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly Agree. Below 1 to less than 1.5 considered to be - Strongly disagree, more than 1.5 to less than 2.5 - Disagree, more than 2.5 to less than 3.5 - Neural, more than 3.5 to less than 4.5 - Agree, more than 4.5 – Strongly agree. The Mean Ranking method between monthly income and consumer purchase intension reveals consumer who have monthly income from 5000 – 10000 are neutral, Consumers from monthly income 10001 and above agreed dominantly to the factors of purchase intension on organic food.

Conclusion:

In general, consumers hold a positive attitude towards organic food. It concludes that the respondents assume it is wise, good and important to buy organic food. Based on the results, the consumer attitude factors are proved to have influence on consumer attitude towards organic food. In other words, the more conscious consumers are of their health, the more knowledge or experiences they obtained, or the more positive in their individual beliefs regarding the good effects of consuming organic food, it results as the more positive in their attitude. The result has concluded a positive relation between consumer's attitude and purchase intention. In other words, if consumers hold a positive attitude towards organic food, it would be more likely to lead to purchase intention. Consumer knowledge, health consciousness, Environmental concern, Personal norms and Subjective Norms are positive in results. Consumers have to step forward to attain the benefits of Organic food.

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